

Multi fuzzifying topology

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Abstract: In this paper, Characterizations of stratified and transitive L -topologies and multi-fuzzifying topology are introduced. First we introduce the concepts of stratified and transitive L -co-topology and stratified and transitive L -closure operator to characterize the concept of stratified and transitive L -topology, where L is a complete MV -algebra. Second, we introduce the concepts of multi-fuzzifying topology, L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system, L -fuzzifying co-contiguity, L -fuzzifying interior operator and L -fuzzifying closure operator to characterize multi-fuzzifying topology, where L is a completely distributive complete residuated lattice satisfying the double negation law, Characterizations of stratified and transitive L -topology are introduced where L is a complete MV -algebra, Characterizations of multi-fuzzifying topology are introduced where L is a completely distributive complete residuated lattice in which the double negation law is satisfied.

Key words: Multi Fuzzifying Topology; L -fuzzifying co-contiguity, MV -algebra

1. Introduction

Since the theory of fuzzy sets was introduced by [Zadeh (13)], many topological notions were introduced and discussed in fuzzy setting. In [Chang (2)], introduced and studied the notion of fuzzy topology as a crisp subset of the family of fuzzy subsets of an ordinary set. Also, [Lowen (7)], [Hutton (6)], [Pu and Liu (9)], and [Wong (10, 11)], discussed respectively various aspects of fuzzy topology where in their approaches the fuzzy topology was defined also as a crisp subset of the fuzzy power set of a nonempty set. [Goguen(3)], introduced the concept of L -set (L -fuzzy set) as a generalization of the concept of fuzzy set where L is some type of lattice. It is worth to mention that [Höhle (5)] used L as a complete MV -algebra but [Ying (12)] used L as a complete residuated lattice. The concept of complete residuated lattice was introduced by [Pavelka (8)]. The concept of L -fuzzifying topology appeared in [Höhle (4)] under the name " L -fuzzy topology " (cf. Definition 4.6, Proposition 4.11 in [Höhle (4)] where L is a completely distributive complete lattice. In the case of $L = [0, 1]$ this terminology traces back to [Ying (12)] studied the fuzzifying topology and elementarily developed fuzzy topology from a new direction with semantic method of continuous valued logic. Fuzzifying topology (resp. L -Fuzzifying topology) in the sense of M. S. Ying (resp. U. Höhle) was introduced as a fuzzy subset (resp. an L -Fuzzy subset) of the power set of an ordinary set. [Höhle (5)] introduced and studied a characterization of stratified and transitive L -topology by stratified and transitive L -interior operator K , where L is a complete MV -algebra. A characterization of L -fuzzifying topology by L -fuzzifying neighborhood system, where L is a completely distributive, was given also in [Höhle (5)]. Finally, [Höhle (5)] introduced a

characterizations of stratified and transitive L -topology by L -contiguity and L -fuzzifying topology, where L is a completely distributive complete MV-algebra. In this paper we introduce and discuss a generalization of a result introduced by [Höhle (5)] in L -fuzzifying topology. Mainly we add Characterizations of stratified and transitive L -topology and multi fuzzifying topology. In Section 1, Lattice theory and basic concepts are introduced. In Section 2, Characterizations of multi fuzzifying topology are introduced where L is a completely distributive complete residuated lattice in which the double negation law is satisfied. In Section 3, L -fuzzifying neighborhood and L -fuzzifying closure operations are considered.

1.1. Lattice theory and basic concepts

Definition 1.1. (Höhle (5)). The double negation law in a complete residuated lattice L is given as follows: $\forall a, b \in L, (a \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = a$.

Definition 1.2. (Höhle (5)). A structure $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is called a strictly two-sided commutative quantale iff

(1) $(L, \vee, \wedge, \perp, \top)$ is a complete lattice whose greatest and least element are \top, \perp respectively,

(2) $(L, *, \top)$ is a commutative monoid,

(3)(a) $*$ is distributive over arbitrary joins, i.e.,

$$a * \bigvee_{j \in J} b_j = \bigvee_{j \in J} (a * b_j) \quad \forall a \in L, \forall \{b_j \mid j \in J\} \subseteq L,$$

(b) \rightarrow is a binary operation on L defined by :

$$a \rightarrow b = \bigvee_{\lambda * a \leq b} \lambda \quad \forall a, b \in L.$$

Definition 1.3. (Höhle (5)). A structure $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is called a complete MV-algebra iff the following conditions are satisfied:

(1) $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is a strictly two-sided commutative quantale,

(2) $\forall a, b \in L, (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow b = a \vee b$.

Definition 1.4. (Pavelka (8), Ying (12)). A structure $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is called a complete residuated lattice iff

(1) $(L, \vee, \wedge, \perp, \top)$ is a complete lattice whose greatest and least element are \top, \perp respectively,

(2) $(L, *, \top)$ is a commutative monoid, i.e.,

(a) $*$ is a commutative and associative binary operation on L , and

(b) $\forall a \in L, a * \top = \top * a = a$,

(3)(a) $*$ is isotone,

(b) \rightarrow is a binary operation on L which is antitone in the first and isotone in the second variable,

(c) \rightarrow is couple with $*$ as: $a * b \leq c$ iff $a \leq b \rightarrow c \quad \forall a, b, c \in L$.

Definition 1.5. (Birkhoff (1)). Let L be a complete lattice. We say that \wedge is distributive over arbitrary joins iff

$$\forall \{\alpha_j : j \in J\} \text{ and } \forall \alpha \in L, \alpha \wedge (\bigvee_{j \in J} \alpha_j) = \bigvee_{j \in J} (\alpha \wedge \alpha_j).$$

Corollary 1.1. $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is a complete MV- algebra iff $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is a complete residuated lattice satisfies the additional property (MV) $(a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow b = a \vee b \quad \forall a, b \in L$.

Definition 1.6. (Höhle (5)). A structure $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is called a complete MV- algebra iff the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) $(L, \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, \perp, \top)$ is a strictly two-sided commutative quantale,
- (2) $\forall a, b \in L, (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow b = a \vee b$.

Theorem 1.1 (Corollary 3.15 [Höhle (5)]). Let $(L, \leq, *)$ be a complete MV- algebra and $\odot = \wedge$. Furthermore let (L, \leq) be a completely distributive lattice complete MV- algebra. Then L -fuzzifying topologies, L -fuzzy contiguity relations and stratified and transitive L -topologies are equivalent concepts.

2. Multi Fuzzifying Topology

Definition 2.1. Let X be a nonempty set and. $[X]^m$ is the set of all msets whose elements are in X such that no element in the mset occurs more than m times. The power mset $P([X]^m)$ of X is the set of all sub msets of X . An element $\mathcal{T} : P([X]^m) \rightarrow I$ is called an multi- fuzzifying topology on X iff it satisfies the following axioms:

- (1) $\mathcal{T}(X) = \mathcal{T}(\phi) = 1$,
- (2) $\forall A, B \in P([X]^m), \mathcal{T}(A \cap B) \geq \mathcal{T}(A) \wedge \mathcal{T}(B)$,
- (3) $\forall \{A_j | j \in J\} \subseteq P([X]^m), \mathcal{T}(\bigcup_{j \in J} A_j) \geq \bigwedge_{j \in J} \mathcal{T}(A_j)$. The pair (X, \mathcal{T}) is called an multi- fuzzifying topological space.

Example 2.1. Let $X = \{x, x, y, y\}$, then $[X]^m = \{\frac{2}{x}, \frac{2}{y}\}$

and $P([X]^m) = \{\phi, \frac{2}{x}, \frac{2}{y}, \frac{1}{\{x\}_2}, \frac{1}{\{y\}_2}, \frac{4}{\{x,y\}}, \frac{2}{\{x,y\}_{2,1}}, \frac{2}{\{x,y\}_{1,2}}, \frac{1}{\{x,y\}_{2,2}}\}$. Define,

$$\mathcal{T}(A) = \begin{cases} 1 & A = \phi, \frac{1}{\{x,y\}_{2,2}} \\ \frac{1}{2} & A = \frac{2}{x}, \frac{2}{y}, \frac{1}{\{x\}_2}, \frac{1}{\{y\}_2} \\ \frac{1}{3} & A = \frac{4}{\{x,y\}}, \frac{2}{\{x,y\}_{2,1}}, \frac{2}{\{x,y\}_{1,2}} \end{cases}$$

Then \mathcal{T} is multi- fuzzifying topology on X .

Remark 2.1 when $m = 1$, multi- fuzzifying topology \Rightarrow fuzzifying topology.

Definition 2.2. Let X be a nonempty set. A map $\mathcal{F} : P ([X]^m) \rightarrow I$ is called an multi-fuzzifying co-topology (or the family of multi-fuzzifying closed sets) if it satisfies the following axioms:

- (1) $\mathcal{F}(X) = \mathcal{F}(\phi) = 1$,
- (2) $\forall A, B \in P ([X]^m), \mathcal{F}(A \cup B) \geq \mathcal{F}(A) \wedge \mathcal{F}(B)$,
- (3) $\forall \{A_j | j \in J\} \subseteq P ([X]^m), \mathcal{F}(\bigcap_{j \in J} A_j) \geq \bigwedge_{j \in J} \mathcal{F}(A_j)$.

Definition 2.3 The family of multi- fuzzifying closed sets, denoted by $F \in I^P ([X]^m)$, is defined as follows: $F(A) = \tau(X - A)$ where $X - A$ is the complement of A .

Definition 2.4 Let (X, τ) be an multi- fuzzifying topological space and $A \subseteq X$, Let $x \in X$. The multi-fuzzifying neighbourhood system of x , denoted by $N_x \in I^P ([X]^m)$, is defined as follows:

$$N_x(A) = \bigvee_{x \in B \subseteq A} \tau(B).$$

Proposition 2.1. Let (X, τ) be an multi-fuzzifying topological space and let $A, B \in P ([X]^m)$. Then $\forall x \in X$,

- (1) $N_x(X) = \top, N_x(\phi) = \perp$,
- (2) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow N_x(A) \leq N_x(B)$,
- (3) If \wedge is distributive over arbitrary joins.

Then $N_x(A \cap B) = N_x(A) \wedge N_x(B)$,

- (4) $N_x(A) \leq \bigvee_{y \in X - B} (N_y(A) \vee N_x(B)) \quad \forall B \in P ([X]^m)$.

Proof. (1)(a) $N_x(X) = \bigvee_{x \in B \subseteq X} \tau(B) = \top$ because $\tau(X) = \top$.

(1)(b) $N_x(\phi) = \bigvee_{x \in H \subseteq \phi} \tau(H) = \perp$.

(2) $N_x(A) = \bigvee_{x \in H \subseteq A} \tau(H) \leq \bigvee_{x \in H \subseteq B} \tau(H) = N_x(B)$.

(3) From (2), we have $N_x(A \cap B) \leq N_x(A) \wedge N_x(B)$, and

$$\begin{aligned} N_x(A \cap B) &= \bigvee_{x \in H \subseteq A \cap B} \tau(H) = \bigvee_{x \in H_1 \cap H_2 \subseteq A \cap B} \tau(H_1 \cap H_2) \geq \bigvee_{x \in H_1 \subseteq A, x \in H_2 \subseteq B} \tau(H_1 \cap H_2) \\ &\geq \bigvee_{x \in H_1 \subseteq A, x \in H_2 \subseteq B} (\tau(H_1) \wedge \tau(H_2)) \geq \bigvee_{x \in H_1 \subseteq A, x \in H_2 \subseteq B} (\tau(H_1) \wedge \tau(H_2)) \\ &= \bigvee_{x \in H_1 \subseteq A} \tau(H_1) \wedge \bigvee_{x \in H_2 \subseteq B} \tau(H_2) = \varphi_x(A) \wedge \varphi_x(B). \end{aligned}$$

(4) Let x be a fixed point in X and let A, G be subsets of X s.t. $x \in G \subseteq A$. Now,

(a) for every $B \in P(X)$ s.t. $G \cap (X - B) \neq \phi$, there exists $y_0 \in G \cap (X - B)$.

Now, $N_{y_0}(A) = \bigvee_{y_0 \in H \subseteq A} \tau(H) \geq \tau(G)$. Hence $\bigvee_{y \in X-B} N_y(A) \geq N_{y_0}(A) \geq \tau(G)$. And

(b) for every $B \in P(X)$ s.t. $G \cap (X - B) = \phi$, $N_x(B) = \bigvee_{x \in M \subseteq A \cap B} \tau(M) \geq \tau(G)$.

Hence $(\bigvee_{y \in X-B} N_y(A)) \vee N_x(B) \geq \bigvee_{x \in G \subseteq A} \tau(G) = N_x(A) \quad \forall B \in P([X]^m)$.

Corollary 2.1 $\bigwedge_{x \in A} N_x(A) = \tau(A)$.

Theorem 2.1 For any $x \in X$, $A \in P([X]^m)$, $\bigwedge_{x \in A} \bigvee_{x \in B \subseteq A} \tau(B) = \tau(A)$

Definition 2.5. The multi-fuzzifying derived set $d_\tau(A)$ of A is defined as follows:

$$d_\tau(A)(x) = \bigwedge_{B \cap (A - \{x\}) = \phi} (1 - N_x(B)).$$

Lemma 2.1. $d_\tau(A)(x) = 1 - N_x((X - A) \cup \{x\})$.

Definition 2.6. The multi-fuzzifying closure $\bar{A} \in I^X$ of $A \in P([X]^m)$ is defined as follows:

$$\bar{A}(x) = \bigwedge_{x \notin B \supseteq A} (1 - F(B)).$$

Lemma 2.1. $\bar{A}(x) = 1 - N_x(X - A)$.

Definition 2.7. For any $A \subseteq X$, the interior $A^\circ \in I^X$ of A , is defined as follows: $A^\circ(x) = N_x(A)$.

3. On multi-fuzzifying neighbourhoods and multi-fuzzifying closure operations

Definition 3.1. Let X be a nonempty set. A map $()^- : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L^X$ is called an multi-fuzzifying closure operator if $()^-$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$(1^-) \quad (\phi)^- = 1_\phi,$$

$$(2^-) \quad (A \cup B)^- = (A)^- \vee (B)^-,$$

$$(3^-) \quad A \leq (A)^-,$$

$$(4^-) \quad (A)^-(x) \leq \bigwedge_{y \notin B} ((A)^-(y) \wedge (B)^-(x)).$$

The multi-fuzzifying closure operator $()^-$ defined in Definition 3.1 induced by the multi-fuzzifying topology τ will be denoted in this Section by cl_τ and one can have it as follows:

$$cl_\tau(A)(x) = N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp \quad \forall x \in X.$$

Remark 3.1. One can observe that the statements in Proposition 2.1 are generalizations of the corresponding statements in Proposition 2.12 (Höhle, (1999)[22]). Note that if L satisfies the completely distributive law, then it satisfies that \wedge is distributive over arbitrary joins.

Proposition 3.1. Let (X, τ) be an multi-fuzzifying topological space. Then:

- (1) If L satisfies the double negation law, then $N_x(A) = cl_\tau(X - A)(x) \rightarrow \perp$,
- (3) $A \leq cl_\tau(A)$,
- (4) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow cl_\tau(A) \leq cl_\tau(B)$,
- (5) $cl_\tau(A \cup B) = cl_\tau(A) \vee cl_\tau(B)$.

Proof. (1) Since $cl_\tau(X - A)(x) = N_x(A) \rightarrow \perp$, then

$$\varphi_x(A) = (\varphi_x(A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = cl_\tau(X - A)(x) \rightarrow \perp.$$

$$(2) cl_\tau(\phi)(x) = \varphi_x(X) \rightarrow \perp = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp \forall x \in X. \text{ Then } cl_\tau(\phi) = 1_\phi.$$

$$(3) \text{ If } x \in A, \text{ then } cl_\tau(A)(x) = N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top = A(x).$$

If $x \notin A$, then $cl_\tau(A)(x) \geq A(x)$. Hence $cl_\tau(A) \geq A$.

$$(4) \text{ Let } A \subseteq B. \text{ Then } cl_\tau(A)(x) = N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp \leq N_x(X - B) \rightarrow \perp = cl_\tau(B)(x).$$

(5)

$$\begin{aligned} cl_\tau(A \cup B) &= N_x(X - (A \cup B)) \rightarrow \perp = N_x((X - A) \cap (X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (N_x(X - A) \wedge N_x(X - B)) \rightarrow \perp = (N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (N_x(X - B) \rightarrow \perp) = cl_\tau(A) \vee cl_\tau(B). \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.2. A stratified and transitive L -topology τ on a nonempty set X is a subset of L^X satisfies the following conditions:

$$(01) 1_X, 1_\phi \in \tau,$$

$$(02) g_1, g_2 \in \tau \Rightarrow g_1 \wedge g_2 \in \tau,$$

$$(03) \{g_j \mid j \in J\} \subseteq \tau \Rightarrow \bigvee_{j \in J} g_j \in \tau,$$

$$\left(\sum 1 \right) g \in \tau, a \in L \Rightarrow (a.1_X) * g \in \tau, \text{ (Truncation Condition)}$$

$$(T1) g \in \tau, a \in L \Rightarrow (a.1_X) \vee g \in \tau, \text{ (Translation-invariance)}$$

$$(T2) g \in \tau, a \in L \Rightarrow g \triangleright (a.1_X) \in \tau. \text{ (Co-Stratification)}$$

The pair (X, τ) is called a stratified and transitive L -topological space.

Definition 3.3. Let X be a nonempty set. A map $K : L^X \rightarrow L^X$ is called a stratified and transitive interior operator if K satisfies the following conditions:

$$(K_0) K(1_X) = 1_X,$$

$$(K_1) f \leq g \Rightarrow K(f) \leq K(g),$$

$$(K_2) K(f) \wedge K(g) \leq K(f \wedge g),$$

$$(K_3) K(f) \leq f,$$

$$(K_4) K(f) \leq K(K(f)),$$

$$(K_5) (a.1_X) * K(f) \leq K((a.1_X) * f),$$

$$(K_6) (a.1_X) \vee K(f) = K((a.1_X) \vee f).$$

Definition 3.4. Let X be a nonempty set. An element $c \in L^{X \times P}([X]^m)$ is called an L -fuzzy contiguity relation on X iff c fulfills the following axioms:

$$(c_1) c(x, \phi) = \perp \quad \forall x \in X.$$

$$(c_2) c(x, A \cup B) = c(x, A) \vee c(x, B), \quad (\text{Distributivity}),$$

$$(c_3) c(x, A) = \top, \quad \text{whenever } x \in A,$$

$$(c_4) (\bigwedge_{y \in B} c(y, A)) \wedge c(x, B) \leq c(x, A). \quad (\text{Transitivity}).$$

Theorem 3.1. If L is a complete MV -algebra, then the concept of stratified and transitive L -topology, and the concept of stratified and transitive L -interior operator are equivalent notions.

Theorem 3.2 (Proposition 3.13 [5]). Let (X, τ) be an multi-fuzzifying topological space, and let L satisfies the completely distributive law then the L -fuzzifying neighborhood system $(N_x)_{x \in X}$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$(f_1) N_x(X) = \top, \quad \forall x \in X, \quad (\text{Boundary conditions})$$

$$(f_2) N_x(A \cap B) = N_x(A) \wedge N_x(B), \quad (\text{Intersection property})$$

$$(u_3) N_x(A) = \perp \quad \text{whenever } x \notin A$$

$$(u_4) N_x(A) \leq \bigvee_{y \notin B} (N_y(A) \vee N_x(B)) \quad \forall B \in P(X). \quad \text{Furthermore } \tau(A) = \bigwedge_{x \in A} \varphi_x(A) \quad \forall A \in P([X]^m).$$

Theorem 3.3 (Proposition 3.14 [5]). let L satisfies the completely distributive law and Let $(N_x)_{x \in X}$ be a system satisfies the properties $(f_1), (f_2), (u_3), (u_4)$ in Theorem 3.2 above . Then $(N_x)_{x \in X}$ induces an multi-

fuzzifying topology τ on X by $\tau(A) = \bigwedge_{x \in A} N_x(A) \quad \forall A \in P([X]^m)$. Moreover the following formula holds $N_x(A) = \bigvee_{x \in B \subseteq A} \tau(B)$.

Theorem 1.4.4 (Corollary 3.15 [Höhle (5)]). Let $(L, \leq, *)$ be a complete MV -algebra and $\odot = \wedge$. Furthermore let (L, \leq) be a completely distributive lattice complete MV -algebra. Then multi-fuzzifying topologies, L -fuzzy contiguity relations and stratified and transitive L -topologies are equivalent concepts.

3.2. Some Characterizations of stratified and transitive L -topology

In this section L is assumed to be a complete MV -algebra.

Definition 3.2.1. Define the binary operator \otimes on L is defined as follows:

$$\alpha \otimes \beta = ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp) * (\beta \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp$$

Definition 3.2.2. Define the binary operator \bigtriangleleft on L is defined as follows:

$$\alpha \bigtriangleleft \beta = \bigvee_{\xi \in L, \xi \wedge \beta \leq \alpha} \xi.$$

Definition 3.2.3. A stratified and transitive L -co-topology F on a nonempty set X is a subset of L^X satisfies the following conditions:

$$(co - 01) \quad 1_X, 1_\phi \in F,$$

$$(co - 02) \quad g_1, g_2 \in F \Rightarrow g_1 \vee g_2 \in F,$$

$$(co - 03) \quad \{g_j | j \in J\} \subseteq F \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{j \in J} g_j \in F,$$

$$(co - \sum 1) \quad g \in F, \alpha \in L \Rightarrow (\alpha \cdot 1_X) \otimes g \in F,$$

$$(co - T_2) \quad g \in F, \alpha \in L \Rightarrow g \bigtriangleleft \alpha \cdot 1_X \in F.$$

By making use of the concept of stratified and transitive L -co-topology we characterize the stratified and transitive L -topology.

Theorem 3.2.1. Let τ be a stratified and transitive L -topology on X . Define $F_\tau : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as: $F_\tau = \{g \in L^X | (g \rightarrow \perp) \in \tau\}$. Then F_τ is a stratified and transitive L -co-topology on X induces by a stratified and transitive L -topology τ on X . Let F be a stratified and transitive L -co-topology on X . Define $\tau_F : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as: $\tau_F = \{g \in L^X | (g \rightarrow \perp) \in F\}$. Then τ_F is a stratified and transitive L -topology on X induces by a stratified and transitive L -co-topology F on X . Furthermore $\tau_{F_\tau} = \tau$ and $F_{\tau_F} = F$.

Proof. (A) $(co - 01) \quad 1_X \in \tau \Rightarrow (1_X \rightarrow \perp) = 1_\phi \in F_\tau$ and $1_\phi \in \tau \Rightarrow (1_\phi \rightarrow \perp) = 1_X \in F_\tau$.

$$(co - 02) \quad g_1, g_2 \in F_\tau \Rightarrow (g_1 \rightarrow \perp), (g_2 \rightarrow \perp) \in \tau \Rightarrow (g_1 \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (g_2 \rightarrow \perp) = (g_1 \vee g_2) \rightarrow \perp \in \tau$$

$$\Rightarrow (g_1 \vee g_2) \in F_\tau.$$

$$(co-03) \{g_j | j \in J\} \subseteq F_\tau \Rightarrow \{g_j \rightarrow \perp | j \in J\} \subseteq \tau \Rightarrow \bigvee_{j \in J} (g_j \rightarrow \perp) = \bigwedge_{j \in J} g_j \rightarrow \perp \in \tau \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{j \in J} g_j \in F_\tau.$$

$$(co-\sum 1) g \in F_\tau, \alpha \in L \Rightarrow (g \rightarrow \perp) \in \tau, (\alpha \rightarrow \perp) \in L \Rightarrow ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X) * (g \rightarrow \perp) \in \tau$$

$$\Rightarrow (((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X) * (g \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \in F_\tau \Rightarrow (\alpha.1_X) \otimes g \in F_\tau.$$

$$(co-T_2) g \in F_\tau, \alpha \in L \Rightarrow (g \rightarrow \perp) \in \tau, \alpha \in L$$

$$\Rightarrow (g \rightarrow \perp) \triangleright ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X) \in \tau \Rightarrow \left(\bigwedge_{\lambda \in L, \lambda \vee (\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X \geq g \rightarrow \perp} \lambda \right) \rightarrow \perp$$

$$= \bigvee_{(\lambda \rightarrow \perp) \in L, (\lambda \rightarrow \perp) \wedge \alpha.1_X \leq g} (\lambda \rightarrow \perp) = g \triangleleft \alpha.1_X \in F_\tau.$$

$$(B) (O1) 1_X \in F \Rightarrow (1_X \rightarrow \perp) = 1_\phi \in \tau_F \text{ and } 1_\phi \in F \Rightarrow (1_\phi \rightarrow \perp) = 1_X \in \tau_F.$$

$$(O2) \text{ Let } g_1, g_2 \in \tau_F \Rightarrow (g_1 \rightarrow \perp), (g_2 \rightarrow \perp) \in F \Rightarrow (g_1 \rightarrow \perp) \vee (g_2 \rightarrow \perp) \in F$$

$$\Rightarrow (g_1 \wedge g_2) \rightarrow \perp \in F \Rightarrow (g_1 \wedge g_2) \in \tau_F.$$

$$(O3) \{g_j | j \in J\} \subseteq \tau_F \Rightarrow \{g_j \rightarrow \perp | j \in J\} \subseteq F \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{j \in J} (g_j \rightarrow \perp) \in F = \bigvee_{j \in J} g_j \rightarrow \perp \in F$$

$$\Rightarrow \bigvee_{j \in J} g_j \in \tau_F.$$

$$(\sum 1) g \in \tau_F, \alpha \in L \Rightarrow (g \rightarrow \perp) \in F, (\alpha \rightarrow \perp) \in L \Rightarrow ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X) \otimes (g \rightarrow \perp) \in F$$

$$\Rightarrow ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X) \otimes (g \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \in \tau_F \Rightarrow ((\alpha.1_X) * g) \in \tau_F.$$

$$(T2) g \in \tau_F, \alpha \in L \Rightarrow (g \rightarrow \perp) \in F, (\alpha \rightarrow \perp) \in L \Rightarrow (g \rightarrow \perp) \triangleleft ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X) \in F$$

$$\Rightarrow ((g \rightarrow \perp) \triangleleft ((\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X)) \rightarrow \perp \in \tau_F \Rightarrow \left(\bigvee_{\lambda \in L, \lambda \wedge (\alpha \rightarrow \perp).1_X \leq g \rightarrow \perp} \lambda \right) \rightarrow \perp \in \tau_F$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\bigwedge_{(\lambda \rightarrow \perp) \in L, (\lambda \rightarrow \perp) \vee \alpha.1_X \geq g} (\lambda \rightarrow \perp) \right) \in \tau_F \Rightarrow \bigwedge_{\lambda \in L, \lambda \vee \alpha.1_X \geq g} \lambda \in \tau_F \Rightarrow g \triangleright (\alpha.1_X) \in \tau_F.$$

$$(C) \tau_{F_\tau} = \{g \in L^X | (g \rightarrow \perp) \in F_\tau\} = \{g \in L^X | (g \in \tau) = \tau \text{ and } F_{\tau_F} = \{g \in L^X | (g \rightarrow \perp) \in \tau_F\}$$

$$= \{g \in L^X | (g \in F)\} = F.$$

Remark 3.2.1. (1) From conditions (01) and $(\sum 1)$ in Definition 1.4.3 one can deduce that $\forall \alpha \in L, \alpha.1_X \in \tau$ (Indeed, from (01) we have that $1_X \in \tau$ so that $\forall \alpha \in L$, one can have from $(\sum 1)$ that $\alpha.1_X * 1_X \in \tau$, i.e., $\alpha.1_X \in \tau$ because $\alpha.1_X * 1_X = \alpha.1_X$).

(2) We note that Condition (T_1) in Definition 1.4.3 can be obtained from conditions (01), (03) and $(\sum 1)$ (Indeed, from (01) and $(\sum 1)$ we have as above that $\forall \alpha \in L, \alpha.1_X \in \tau$. Now let $g \in \tau$ so that from (03), we have $(\alpha.1_X) \vee g \in \tau$).

Definition 3.2.4. Let X be a nonempty set. An element $C \in (L^X)^{L^X}$ is called a stratified and transitive L -closure operator on X if C satisfies the following conditions:

$$(C0) \ C(1_\phi) = 1_\phi,$$

$$(C1) \ f \leq g \Rightarrow C(f) \leq C(g),$$

$$(C2) \ C(f) \vee C(g) \geq C(f \vee g),$$

$$(C3) \ C(f) \geq f,$$

$$(C4) \ C(f) \geq C(C(f)),$$

$$(C5) \ (\alpha.1_X) \otimes C(f) \geq C((\alpha.1_X) \otimes f),$$

$$(C6) \ (\alpha.1_X) \wedge C(f) = C((\alpha.1_X) \wedge f).$$

The second characterization of stratified and transitive L -topology in this section is given now by making use of stratified and transitive L -closure operator.

Theorem 3.2.2. Let K be a stratified and transitive L -interior operator. Define

$C_K : L^X \rightarrow L^X$ as: $C_K(f) = K(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp$. Then C_K is a stratified and transitive L -closure operator on X induces by a stratified and transitive L -interior operator K on X . Let C be a stratified and transitive L -closure operator on X . Define $K_C : L^X \rightarrow L^X$ as: $K_C(f) = C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp$. Then K_C is a stratified and transitive L -interior operator on X induces by a stratified and transitive L -closure operator C on X . Furthermore $K_{C_K} = K$ and $C_{K_C} = C$.

Proof. (A) $(C0) \ C_K(1_\phi) = K(1_\phi \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = K(1_X) \rightarrow \perp = 1_X \rightarrow \perp = 1_\phi$

$$(C1) \ \text{Let } f \leq g. \text{ So, } C_K(f) = K(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \leq K(g \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = C_K g$$

$$\begin{aligned} (C2) \ C_K(f) \vee C_K(g) &= (K(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (K(g \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = (K(f \rightarrow \perp) \wedge K(g \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &\geq K((f \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (g \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= K((f \vee g) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = C_K(f \vee g), \end{aligned}$$

$$(C3) \ C_K(f) = K(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \geq (f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = f,$$

$$(C4) \ C_K(f) = K(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \geq K(K(f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = K((C_K(f) \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = C_K(C_K(f)),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (C5) \quad C_K((\alpha.1_X) \otimes f) &= K(((\alpha.1_X) \otimes f) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = K((\alpha.1_X) \rightarrow \perp) * (f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \\
 &\leq ((\alpha.1_X) \rightarrow \perp * K(f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = (\alpha.1_X) \rightarrow \perp * (C_K(f) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \\
 &= \alpha.1_X \otimes C_K(f),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (C6) \quad C_K((\alpha.1_X) \wedge f) &= K(((\alpha.1_X) \wedge f) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = K(((\alpha.1_X) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\
 &= (((\alpha.1_X) \rightarrow \perp) \vee K(f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = (\alpha.1_X) \wedge C_K(f)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$(B) \quad (K0) \quad K_C(1_X) = C(1_X \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = C(1_\phi) \rightarrow \perp = 1_\phi \rightarrow \perp = 1_X,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (K1) \quad f \leq g &\Rightarrow g \rightarrow \perp \leq f \rightarrow \perp = C(g \rightarrow \perp) \leq C(f \rightarrow \perp) \\
 &\Rightarrow C(g \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \geq C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \Rightarrow K_C(f) \leq K_C(g)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (K2) \quad K_C(f) \wedge K_C(g) &= (C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (C(g \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = (C(f \rightarrow \perp) \vee C(g \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\
 &\leq C((f \rightarrow \perp) \vee (g \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = C((f \wedge g) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = K_C(f \wedge g),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$(K3) \quad K_C(f) = C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \leq (f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = f,$$

$$(K4) \quad K_C(f) = C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \leq C(C(f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = C(K_C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = K_C(K_C(f)),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (K5) \quad (\alpha.1_X) * K_C(f) &= (\alpha.1_X) * (C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = ((\alpha.1_X \rightarrow \perp) \otimes C(f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\
 &\leq C((\alpha.1_X \rightarrow \perp) \otimes (f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp = C(((\alpha.1_X) * f) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = K_C((\alpha.1_X) * f),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (K6) \quad \alpha.1_X \vee K_C(f) &= \alpha.1_X \vee (C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = ((\alpha.1_X \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (C(f \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \\
 &= ((\alpha.1_X \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (C(f \rightarrow \perp))) \rightarrow \perp = C(((\alpha.1_X) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (f \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\
 &= C(((\alpha.1_X) \vee f) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = K_C(\alpha.1_X \vee f).
 \end{aligned}$$

(C) One can easily deduce that $K_{C_K} = K$ and $C_{K_C} = C$.

4. Characterizations of multi fuzzifying topology

In this section L is assumed to be a completely distributive complete residuated lattice, where L satisfies the double negation law.

In (Corollary 2.15 [Höhle (5)] (see Theorem 1.4.4)) proved that the L -fuzzy contiguity relations and L -fuzzifying topologies are equivalent notions if L is a completely distributive complete MV-algebra. In the following we prove that L -fuzzy contiguity relations and multi fuzzifying topology are equivalent notions just if L is a completely distributive complete residuated lattice satisfies the double negation law so that we give a generalization of U. Höhle's result.

In [Höhle (5)] from Theorems 1.4.2, 14.3, the concepts of L -fuzzifying topology and L -fuzzifying neighborhood system are equivalent notions. Then our generalization of U. Höhle's result is obtained if we prove that multi fuzzifying contiguity relation and L -fuzzifying neighborhood system are equivalent notions.

Theorem 4.1. Let N_x be an L -fuzzifying neighborhood system. Define

$c_{(\varphi_x)} : X \times P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as : $c_{(N_x)}(x, A) = N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp$. Then $c_{(N_x)}$ is an L -fuzzy contiguity relation induces by L -fuzzifying neighborhood system N_x . Let c be an L -fuzzy contiguity relation. Define $(N_x)_c : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as: $(N_x)_c(A) = c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp$. Then $(N_x)_c$ is an L -fuzzifying neighborhood system induces by L -fuzzy contiguity relation c . Furthermore $c_{(N_x)_c} = c$ and $(N_x)_{c(\varphi_x)} = (N_x)$.

Proof. (A) (c_1) $c_{(N_x)}(x, \phi) = N_x(X - \phi) \rightarrow \perp = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp$

$$\begin{aligned} (c_2) \quad c_{(N_x)}(x, A \cup B) &= N_x(X - (A \cup B)) \rightarrow \perp = N_x((X - A) \cap (X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= ((N_x(X - A)) \wedge (N_x(X - B))) \rightarrow \perp = (N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (N_x(X - B) \rightarrow \perp) \\ &= c(x, A) \vee c(x, B), \end{aligned}$$

$$(c_3) \quad \text{Let } x \in A. \text{ Then } c_{(N_x)}(x, A) = N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top$$

$$\begin{aligned} (c_4) \quad c_{(N_x)}(x, A) &= N_x(X - A) \rightarrow \perp \geq (\bigvee_{y \notin B} (N_y(X - A) \vee N_x(B))) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in B} (N_y(X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (N_x(B^c) \rightarrow \perp) = (\bigwedge_{y \in B} c(y, A)) \wedge c(x, B). \end{aligned}$$

$$(B) \quad (f_1) \quad (N_x)_c(X) = c(x, \phi) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top,$$

$$\begin{aligned} (f_2) \quad (N_x)_c(A \cap B) &= c(x, (X - A) \cup (X - B)) \rightarrow \perp = (c(x, X - A) \vee c(x, X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (c(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp) = \varphi_x(A) \wedge \varphi_x(B), \\ &= N_x(A) \wedge N_x(B), \end{aligned}$$

$$(u_3) \quad \text{Let } x \notin A. \text{ Then } (N_x)_c(A) = c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp,$$

$$\begin{aligned} (u_4) \quad (\varphi_x)_c(A) &= c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp \leq ((\bigwedge_{y \in B^c} c(y, X - A)) \wedge c(x, X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= \bigvee_{y \in B^c} (c(y, X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (c(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp) \\ &= \bigvee_{y \notin B} ((\varphi_y)_c(A) \vee (\varphi_x)_c(B)). \end{aligned}$$

$$(C) \quad (\varphi_x)_{c(\varphi_x)}(A) = c_{(\varphi_x)}(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp = (\varphi_x(A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = \varphi_x(A) \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_{(\varphi_x)_c}(x, A) &= (\varphi_x)_c(X - A) \rightarrow \perp = (c(x, A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= c(x, A). \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.1. Let X be a nonempty set. An element $d \in L^{X \times P([X]^m)}$ is called an L -fuzzy co-contiguity relation on X iff d satisfies the following axioms,

$$(co - c_1) d(x, X) = \top \quad \forall x \in X,$$

$$(co - c_2) d(x, A \cap B) = d(x, A) \wedge d(x, B), \quad (\text{Distributivity})$$

$$(co - c_3) d(x, A) = \perp \quad \text{whenever } x \notin A,$$

$$(co - c_4) \bigvee_{y \notin B} d(y, A) \vee d(x, B) \geq d(x, A).$$

Theorem 4.2. Let c be an L -fuzzy contiguity relation on X . Define $d_c : X \times P(X) \rightarrow L$ as: $d_c(x, A) = c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp$. Then d_c is an L -fuzzy co-contiguity relation on X induces by an L -fuzzy contiguity relation c on X . Let d be an L -fuzzy co-contiguity relation on X . Define $c_d : X \times P(X) \rightarrow L$ as: $c_d(x, A) = d(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp$. Then c_d is an L -fuzzy contiguity relation on X induces by L -fuzzy co-contiguity relation d on X . Furthermore $c_{d_c} = c$ and $d_{c_d} = d$.

Proof. (A) $(co - c_1) d_c(x, X) = c(x, \phi) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top$,

$$\begin{aligned} (co - c_2) d_c(x, A \cap B) &= c(x, (X - A) \cup (X - B)) \rightarrow \perp = (c(x, X - A) \vee c(x, X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (c(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp) = d_c(x, A) \wedge d_c(x, B), \end{aligned}$$

$(co - c_3)$ Let $x \in X - A$. Then $c(x, X - A) = \top$. So, $d_c(x, A) = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp$,

$$\begin{aligned} (co - c_4) d_c(x, A) &= c(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp \leq ((\bigwedge_{y \in B^c} c(y, X - A)) \wedge c(x, X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &\leq \bigvee_{y \notin B} (c(y, X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (c(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp) = \bigvee_{y \notin B} d_c(y, A) \vee d_c(x, B). \end{aligned}$$

(B) $(c_1) c_d(x, \phi) = d(x, X) \rightarrow \perp = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp$,

$$\begin{aligned} (c_2) c_d(x, A \cup B) &= d(x, (X - A) \cap (X - B)) \rightarrow \perp = (d(x, X - A) \wedge d(x, X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (d(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (d(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp) = c_d(x, A) \vee c_d(x, B), \end{aligned}$$

(c_3) Let $x \in A$. Then $c_d(x, A) = d(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top$,

$$\begin{aligned} (c_4) c_d(x, A) &= d(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp \geq (\bigvee_{y \notin B^c} d(y, X - A)) \vee d(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \notin B^c} d(y, X - A) \rightarrow \perp \wedge (d(x, X - B) \rightarrow \perp) \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in B} c_d(y, A) \wedge c_d(x, B) \end{aligned}$$

(C) $d_{c_d}(x, A) = c_d(x, X - A) \rightarrow \perp = (d(x, A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = d(x, A)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} c_{d_c}(x, A) &= d_c(x, A^c) \rightarrow \perp = (c(x, A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= c(x, A). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3. The concepts of multi fuzzifying topology and L -fuzzifying co-topology are equivalent notions.

Definition 4.2. Let X be a nonempty set and Let $x \in X$. The L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system of x is denoted by $\psi_x \in L^P([X]^m)$ and satisfies the following conditions:

$$(co - f_1) \quad \psi_x(\phi) = \perp, \forall x \in X, \text{ (Boundary conditions)}$$

$$(co - f_2) \quad \psi_x(A \cup B) = \psi_x(A) \vee \psi_x(B), \text{ (Intersection property)}$$

$$(co - u_3) \quad \psi_x(A) = \top \text{ whenever } x \in A$$

$$(co - u_4) \quad \psi_x(A) \geq \bigwedge_{y \in B} (\psi_y(A) \wedge \psi_x(B)) \quad \forall B \in P([X]^m).$$

Theorem 4.4. Let φ_x be an L -fuzzifying neighborhood system. Define

$(\psi_x)_{(N_x)} : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as: $(\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(A) = N_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp$. Then $(\psi_x)_{(N_x)}$ is an L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system induces by L -fuzzifying neighborhood system N_x on X . Let ψ_x be an L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system. Define $(\varphi_x)_{(\psi_x)} : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as:

$(N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(A) = \psi_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp$. Then $(N_x)_{(\psi_x)}$ is an L -fuzzifying neighborhood system induces by L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system ψ_x on X . Furthermore $(\psi_x)_{(N_x)_{(\psi_x)}} = \psi_x$ and $(N_x)_{(\psi_x)_{(N_x)}} = N_x$.

Proof. (A) $(co - f_1) (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(\phi) = N_x(X) \rightarrow \perp = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp$.

$$\begin{aligned} (co - f_2) (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(A \cup B) \rightarrow \perp &= N_x((A \cup B) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = N_x((A \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (B \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (N_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (N_x(B \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(A) \vee (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(B). \end{aligned}$$

$$(co - u_3) \text{ Let } x \notin A^c. \text{ Then } N_x(A^c) = \perp \text{ so that } (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(A) = N_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (co - u_4) (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(A) &= N_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \geq \bigvee_{y \notin B^c} (N_y(A \rightarrow \perp) \vee N_x(B^c)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \notin B^c} (N_y(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (N_x(B^c) \rightarrow \perp) \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in B} ((\psi_y)_{(N_y)}(A) \wedge ((\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(B))). \end{aligned}$$

$$(B) (f_1) (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(X) = \psi_x(\phi) \rightarrow \perp = \perp \rightarrow \perp = \top.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (f_2) (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(A \cap B) &= \psi_x((A \cap B) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = (\psi_x((A \rightarrow \perp) \cup (B \rightarrow \perp))) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (\psi_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \vee \psi_x(B \rightarrow \perp)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= (\psi_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \wedge (\psi_x(B \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) = (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(A) \wedge (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(B). \end{aligned}$$

$$(u_3) \text{ Let } x \notin A. \text{ Then } (N_x)_{\psi_x}(A) = \psi_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = \top \rightarrow \perp = \perp.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (u_4) (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(A) &= \psi_x(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp \leq (\bigwedge_{y \in B^c} \psi_y(A \rightarrow \perp) \wedge \psi_x(X - B)) \rightarrow \perp \\ &= \bigvee_{y \in B^c} (\psi_y(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp) \vee (\psi_x(X - B) \rightarrow \perp) \\ &= (\bigvee_{y \notin B} (N_y)_{(\psi_y)}(A)) \vee (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(B). \end{aligned}$$

$$(C) (\psi_x)_{(N_x)(\psi_x)}(A) = (N_x)_{(\psi_x)}(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = (\psi_x(A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = \psi_x(A) \quad \text{and}$$

$$(N_x)_{(\psi_x)(N_x)}(A) = (\psi_x)_{(N_x)}(A \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = (N_x(A) \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \perp = N_x(A).$$

Definition 4.3. Let X be a nonempty set. A map $(\)^\circ: P([X]^m) \rightarrow L^X$ is called an L -fuzzifying interior operator if $(\)^\circ$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$(1^0) (X)^\circ = 1_X,$$

$$(2^0) (A \cap B)^\circ = (A)^\circ \wedge (B)^\circ,$$

$$(3^0) (A)^\circ \leq A,$$

$$(4^0) (A)^\circ(x) \leq \bigvee_{y \notin B} ((A)^\circ(y) \vee (B)^\circ(x)).$$

Theorem 4.5. Let N_x be an L -fuzzifying neighborhood system. Define

$(\)^\circ_N: P([X]^m) \rightarrow L^X$ as: $(A)^\circ_N(x) = N_x(A)$. Then $(\)^\circ_N$ is an L -fuzzifying interior operator induces by L -fuzzifying neighborhood system N_x on X . Let $(\)^\circ$ be an L -fuzzifying interior operator. Define $N_x: P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as: $(N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A) = (A)^\circ(x)$. Then $(N_x)_{(\)^\circ}$ is an L -fuzzifying neighborhood system induces by L -fuzzifying interior operator $(\)^\circ$ on X . Moreover $(N_x)_{(\)^\circ_{N_x}} = N_x$ and $(\)^\circ_{(N_x)_{(\)^\circ}} = (\)^\circ$.

Proof.

$$(A) (1^\circ) (X)^\circ_{N_x}(x) = N_x(X) = \top, \forall x \in X. \quad \text{So, } (X)^\circ_{N_x} = 1_X.$$

$$(2^\circ) (A \cap B)^\circ_{\varphi_x} = N_x(A \cap B) = N_x(A) \wedge N_x(B) = (A)^\circ_{N_x} \wedge (B)^\circ_{N_x},$$

$$(3^\circ) (A)^\circ_{N_x}(x) = N_x(A) \leq A(x),$$

$$(4^\circ) (A)^\circ_{N_x}(x) = N_x(A) \leq \bigvee_{y \notin B} (N_y(A) \vee N_x(B)) = \bigvee_{y \notin B} ((A)^\circ_{N_x}(y) \vee (B)^\circ_{N_x}(x)).$$

$$(B) (f1) (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(X) = (X)^\circ(x) = 1_X(x) = \top, \forall x \in X.$$

$$(f2) (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A \cap B) = (A \cap B)^\circ(x) = (A)^\circ(x) \wedge (B)^\circ(x) = (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A) \wedge (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(B),$$

$$(u3) \text{ Let } x \notin A. \text{ Then, } (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A) = (A)^\circ(x) \leq A(x) = \perp. \text{ So, } (\varphi_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A) = \perp.$$

$$(u4) (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A) = (A)^\circ(x) \leq \bigvee_{y \notin B} ((A)^\circ(y) \vee (B)^\circ(x)) = \bigvee_{y \notin B} ((N_y)_{(\)^\circ}(A) \vee (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(B)).$$

$$(C) (N_x)_{(\)^\circ_{(N_x)}}(A) = (A)^\circ_{(N_x)}(x) = N_x(A) \quad \text{and} \quad (\)^\circ_{(N_x)_{(\)^\circ}}(A)(x) = (N_x)_{(\)^\circ}(A) = (A)^\circ(x).$$

Definition 4.4. Let X be a nonempty set. A map $(\)^-: P([X]^m) \rightarrow L^X$ is called an L -fuzzifying closure operator if $(\)^-$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$(1^-) (\phi)^- = 1_\phi,$$

$$(2^-) (A \cup B)^- = (A)^- \vee (B)^-,$$

$$(3^-) A \leq (A)^-,$$

$$(4^-) (A)^-(x) \leq \bigwedge_{y \notin B} ((A)^-(y) \wedge (B)^-(x)).$$

Theorem 4.6. Let ψ_x be an L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system. Define

$(\)^- : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L^X$ as: $(A)_{\psi}^-(x) = \psi_x(A)$. Then $(\)_{\psi}^-$ is an L -fuzzifying closure operator induces by

L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system ψ_x on X . Let $(\)^-$ be an L -fuzzifying closure operator. Define

$\psi_x : P([X]^m) \rightarrow L$ as: $(\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A) = A^-(x)$. Then $(\psi_x)_{(\)^-}$ is an L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood system induces

by L -fuzzifying closure operator $(\)^-$ on X . Moreover $(\psi_x)_{(\)_{\psi}^-}^- = \psi_x$ and $(\)_{\psi_x(\)^-}^- = (\)^-$.

Proof. (A) $(1^-) (\phi)_{\psi}^-(x) = \psi_x(\phi) = \perp, \forall x \in X$. So, $(\phi)_{\psi}^-(x) = 1_{\phi}$,

$$(2^-) (A \cup B)_{\psi}^-(x) = \psi_x(A \cup B) = \psi_x(A) \vee \psi_x(B) = (A)_{\psi}^-(x) \vee (B)_{\psi}^-(x),$$

$$(3^-) (A)_{\psi}^-(x) = \psi_x(A) \geq A(x),$$

$$(4^-) (A)_{\psi}^-(x) = \psi_x(A) \geq \bigwedge_{y \notin B} (\psi_y(A) \wedge \psi_x(B)) = \bigwedge_{y \notin B} ((A)_{\psi}^-(y) \wedge (B)_{\psi}^-(x)).$$

(B) $(co - f1) (\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(\phi) = \phi^-(x) = 1_{\phi}, \forall x \in X$. So, $(\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(\phi) = \perp$.

$$(co - f2) (\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A \cup B) = (A \cup B)^-(x) = (A)^-(x) \vee (B)^-(x) = (\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A) \vee (\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(B),$$

$(co - u3)$ Let $x \in A$. Then $(\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A) = (A)^-(x) = \top$. So, $(\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A) = \top$,

$$(co - u4) (\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A) = (A)^-(x) \leq \bigwedge_{y \notin B} ((A)^-(y) \wedge (B)^-(x)) = \bigwedge_{y \notin B} (((A) \vee (\psi_x)_{(\)_{\psi_y}^-}^-)(B)).$$

(C) $(\psi_x)_{(\)_{\psi_x}^-}^-(A) = (A)_{\psi}^-(x) = \psi_x(A)$ and $(\)_{\psi_x(\)^-}^- (A) = (\psi_x)_{(\)^-}(A) = (A)^-(x)$.

Remark 4.1. From (Corollary 2.15 [Höhle (1999)] (see Theorem 1.1)) and Theorems 3.2.1, 3.2.2, 4.1, 4.2,4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6 one can have the following Theorem:

Theorem 4.7. If L is a completely distributive complete MV -algebra then the concepts of stratified and transitive L -topologies, stratified and transitive co- L -topologies, stratified and transitive L -interior operators, stratified and transitive L -closure operators, L -fuzzy contiguity relations, L -fuzzifying neighborhood systems, L -fuzzy co-contiguity relations, multi fuzzifying topologies, L -fuzzifying co-topologies, L -fuzzifying co-neighborhood systems, L -fuzzifying interior operators, L -fuzzifying closure operators are equivalent notions.

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References

[1] Birkhoff G. 1967, Lattice theory, 2nd ed.,AMS Providence, RI,.

- [2] Chang C.L., (1968) Fuzzy topological spaces, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 22,182- 190.
- [3] GoguenJ.A.(1967), L-fuzzy sets, J. Math. Anal. Appl., 18,124-172.
- [4] HöhleU.(1980), Upper semicontinuous fuzzy sets and applications, J. Math. Anal. Appl.78,449-472.
- [5] HöhleU.(1999), Characterization of L-topologies by L-valued neighborhoods, in: U. Höhle, S.E.Rodabaugh (Eds.), The Handbooks of Fuzzy Sets Series, Vol.2, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, .pp.289-222.
- [6] HuttonB.,(1974), Normality in fuzzy topological spaces, J. Math. Anal Appl., 44 421-422.
- [7] LowenR.(1974), Fuzzy topological spaces and fuzzy compactness, J. Math. Anal. Appl., 44 , 421-422.
- [8] Pavelka J.(1979), On fuzzy logic II, Z. Math. Logic Gvundlagen Math. 24 119-122.
- [9] PuB. M. , Liu Y. K. (1980), Fuzzy topology(I),Neighborhood structure of a fuzzy point and moore-Smith convergence, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 74, 471-499.
- [10] WongC.K.(1972) , Covering properties of fuzzy topological spaces, J. Math. Anal. Appl., 22 , 497-702.
- [11] WongC.K.(1972), Fuzzy point and local properties of fuzzy topology, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 24 , 214-228.
- [12] YingM.S. (1993), Fuzzifying topology based on complete residuated Lattice-valued logic (I), Fuzzy Sets and Systems 44, 227-272.
- [13] ZadehL.A. (1965), Fuzzy sets, Inform. Control 8 228-242.
- [14] A. A. Yusuf and M. Darus On geometric properties of generalized concave meromorphic functions Asia Matematika : 8, 74-85
- [15] K. Prudhvi Results on fixed points for WC-Mappings satisfying generalized contractive condition in C- metric spaces Asia Matematika 8, 112-117
- [16] Selvaraj Ganesan Nano generalized-locally closed sets in nano topological spaces Asia Matematika 7, 55-61.